

BENDING PLATE WIM SYSTEM ANALYSIS CONSIDERING THE DYNAMICS OF THE LOAD PLATFORM

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Abstract

This paper presents a numerical study on the behavior of weigh in motion systems based on bending plate WIM system. Some important parameters that may role this behavior are modeled: random road roughness, vehicle vertical dynamics, vehicle speed, load platform step's height to the road and dynamics of load platform. Two types of vehicles are evaluated numerically travelling at different speeds and being weighted. Ground reaction force and acceleration time history on several Degree of Freedom (DoF) are used to estimate the error of the measured weight for the rigid platform model. For the flexible platform model, the reaction forces serve as inputs into the Euler-Bernoulli finite element model with consideration of the contact area of the tire by train of loads. Conclusions concerning the importance of platform dynamics are obtained.

Keywords: Bending Plate, Weigh-in-motion, WIM, Dynamics, Road roughness profile, Finite element model.

Résumé

Ce travail présente une étude numérique sur le comportement de systèmes de pesage en marche basée sur le système WIM de bascule à jauges de contraintes. Certains paramètres importants pouvant représenter ce comportement sont: la rugosité aléatoire de la route, la dynamique verticale du véhicule, la vitesse du véhicule, la hauteur de la charge de la plate-forme sur la route et la dynamique de la plate-forme de chargement. Deux types de véhicules sont testés numériquement en se déplaçant à des vitesses différentes et en étant pesés. La force de réaction du sol et l'historique des temps d'accélération à divers degrés de liberté sont utilisés pour estimer l'erreur du poids mesuré pour le modèle à plate-forme rigide. Pour le modèle de plate-forme flexible, les forces de réaction servent d'intrants au modèle d'éléments finis d'Euler-Bernoulli en tenant compte de la zone de contact du pneu par train de marchandises. Des conclusions sur l'importance de la dynamique de la plate-forme sont obtenues.

Mots clés: Barreau de pesage, Pesage en marche, WIM, Dynamique, Profil de rugosité de piste, Modèle éléments finis.

1 Introduction

With the purpose of being able to evaluate the weighing in vehicle movement and to be able to model the main phenomena that occur, this work proposes a numerical study and modeling of these phenomena. Thus, the main objective is to analyze and model the bending plate weighing system of platforms (this technology is based on the measurement of deflection) commonly used in Brazil to verify the individual influence factors: the road roughness, vehicle type load platform step's height to the road and dynamics of load platform in the accuracy of the system. One the main problem is the accurate weight evaluation based on part of the acquired force signal from load cells, which may be superposed to the loads from vehicle's vertical dynamics. Jacob (2011) affirms that there is a typical increase of 10% to 30% in RMS value for good roads and up to 50% to high rough roads.

The finite element method is a computational tool developed around the 1950s and is widely used in various fields of engineering with analysis applications not only mechanical, civil structures, but also analysis of fluids, gases, etc. Currently there are several commercial software available to the engineer so you can use this tool in a more practical way. The importance of the method comes from the possibility of analyzing structures of more diverse forms and geometries, which in an approach by analytical solution would be possible in only some specific and well-defined cases, which is not common in practice. This method starts from the approximation of the differential equations corresponding to a domain, in smaller problems corresponding to subdomains of the general problem. This is possible from the discretization by field of variables in elements (regions) and the hypotheses of continuity and form of variation of this field within the elements (form functions). Specifically, in the case of solids mechanics problems, in general, the displacement field is the field used to be approximated by interpolation functions called shape functions. These functions aim to satisfy the conditions of differentiability and continuity required by the equilibrium differential equations of the analysis in question. From a variational formulation assembled as a function of the potential energy, it is possible to arrive at the respective stiffness matrices of the structural problem in simple cases, and that for more complex cases can be obtained by the numerical integration. The formulation and deduction of the equations for the most diverse types of elements are found in a vast literature such as Bathe (2014), Ferreira (2009) and Reddy (2006) and that will not be the focus of this work.

For bridge weighing, the finite element modeling found in the literature ranges from finite elements of beams to three-dimensional elements that describe the geometry of the bridge. In the case of bending plates specifically, the modeling also varies from simple finite elements of beams to more complex models in plates or shells that better describe the geometry of the load cell type. The weighing platform in this work is modeled as a simply supported Euler-Bernoulli beam, a configuration similar to that found on the field platform where the platform is supported in the cradle of the track at the weighing site. This type of finite element has shape functions of the linear type for the displacement field and is suitable for modeling of beams that are thinned since the Euler model does not consider deformation by cutting. The weighing platform has a thickness that is much smaller than the other two dimensions: width and length.

2 Description of the numerical model

2.1 Road roughness modelling

The road roughness follows ISO 8608 (1995) recommendations that is based on international roughness classes of Power Spectral Density (PSD) for pavement rating. Time histories for the road tracks are simulated and used as input parameters for the vehicle model. The function that describes random surface profile, travelled by the vehicle, according to Gomes *et al.* (2008) is a function of displacement as a function of time, consists of a sum of harmonics, as shown the Equation (1).

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N A_i \sin(\omega_i t + \phi_i) \quad (1)$$

where the phase angle is a random variable generated between $0, 2\pi$. The frequency ω_i can be related with the wave numbers n_i and with the speed of horizontal displacement of the vehicle v as follows, Equation (2):

$$\omega_i = 2\pi n_i v \quad (2)$$

The amplitude for each component of the function A_i (shift) is defined as, Equation (3):

$$A_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N G(n_i) \Delta n_i \quad (3)$$

Thus, the road profile is obtained by Equation (4):

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{G(n_i) \Delta n_i} \sin(\omega_i t + \phi_i) \quad (4)$$

As the front and rear tires don't suffer influence of the track at the same time, the entry of the disturbance must be offset with the time needed to traverse the distance between axles by the amount of length between axes divided by velocity v .

2.2 Modelling the step between load platform and road surface

The link between the platform and the track is modeled as a kind bounce of type step. The deformation of the tire is characterized in the model of the vehicle by their stiffness. For the step modelling purposes, it is assumed the track before and after the load cell has their characteristic roughness. On the surface of the load cell, this roughness is assumed smooth. In order to properly describe the input and output of the load cell must have at least a number of points in space to make sure the discretization in space is enough to represent the roughness of the road profile. More details can be found in (Gaspareto and Gomes, 2016).

2.3 Simulated and Tested Vehicles

There are two types of full vehicles being numerically tested: The type (a) vehicle presents a total mass of 2550 kg. It is assumed a wheelbase Wb of 2.312 m. It has 8 DoF (with four independent suspensions and driver seat, four unsprung masses, pitch, roll and vertical displacements of the vehicle's body mass) that is suitable for model vans/light trucks. Details related to the equation of motion, further parameters and their values can be found in (Dhremmer, 2012). The type (b) vehicle represents an actual passenger bus model IK301 with total mass of 18871 kg, wheelbase of 5.650m and width 2m. It has 10 DoF (with two suspensions bars, driver and passenger seats) that are suitable for bus/medium trucks. More details related to the bus model, equation of motion and values for the parameters can be found in (Sekulic' *et al.*, 2013).

2.4 Model of Load Platform

Two models are tested for the modeling of the phenomenon investigated here: (a) a first model that considers the weighing platform completely rigid, that is, without considering its deformation nor dynamic associated to the platform or interaction with the vehicle (Rigid Platform Model, RPM); (b) a second model where the platform dynamics was considered considering some vibration modes with the associated damping, in the reading of the measured forces (FPM). For the RPM model the vehicle reaction forces are used with the soil in the stretches of the platform using the vehicle, step and track modeling. For the FPM, these forces serve as input to the finite element model of Euler-Bernoulli beam considering the contact area of the tire. The full details of the model can be found in (Gaspareto, 2017)

2.4.1 Simple beam subjected to a moving Load

Yang *et al.* (2004) presents the analytical solution for the case of a simply supported beam subjected to a moving load modeled by a concentrated load force p and velocity v . The following hypotheses are adopted in this study: (a) the bar is homogeneous and of constant cross section, where Euler Bernoulli-Euler's hypothesis is satisfied that the flat sections remain flat after the deformation occurs; (b) only a single moving force is allowed to traverse the beam at a time; (c) initially only the applied force is considered, whereas the inertia effect of that which causes the force is neglected, assumed to be small in comparison with that of the beam; (d) the load moves at a constant velocity v , (e) the damping of the beam is of the Rayleigh type, (f) the beam is initially at rest before the load moves and (g) no consideration is given, initially, on the surface roughness of the beam.

Figure 1- Simply supported beam traversed by a concentrated load p with velocity v .

As shown in Figure 1, a single beam is subjected to a load of magnitude p advancing at a velocity v . Here, $u(x, t)$ denotes the deflection of the beam along the y axis at the position x and time t , L is the beam length, m is mass per unit length, c_e is the external damping coefficient, c_i the internal damping coefficient, E the modulus of elasticity and I the moment of inertia of the beam. Based on the above mentioned assumptions, the equation of motion of the beam can be written as (Equation 5):

$$m\ddot{u} + c_e\dot{u} + c_i I \dot{u}'''' + EIu'''' = p\delta(x - vt) \quad (5)$$

where the lines mean derivatives with respect to the space x and the points mean derivatives with respect to time, t is the time and δ means the Dirac delta function. For a beam with contour conditions simply supported, it is worth (Equation 6):

$$u(0, t) = 0, \quad u(L, t) = 0, \quad EIu''(0, t) = 0, \quad EIu''(L, t) = 0 \quad (6)$$

And for the initial conditions of displacement and initial velocities at any point, null, assuming the beam at rest upon arrival of the moving load (Equation 7):

$$u(x, 0) = 0, \dot{u}(x, 0) = 0 \quad (7)$$

The dynamics of the platform can be modeled according to the presented equation, however the modeling becomes very complex analytically for cases of any platform geometries. Moreover the whole development is for punctual loads traversing the beam. For simplification in the resolution of the equation for the different regions of the weighing platform we use finite element modeling and integration using numerical methods such as the implicit Newmark method. This makes the treatment of the problem more generic and easier to implement as simulation of tire pressure, different cross sections along the length, coupling with vehicle dynamics, etc.

2.4.2 Tire contact area considerations

Each tire is simulated as a train of loads with length (L_c) relative to its contact length with the ground considered constant as a function of the tire radius (40% of the tire radius), values consistent with Castro (2013). The tire force (F_{pneu}) is divided by the total number of discrete loads of the freight train (N) used. In this work is used a discretization of the contact area of the tire with 100 parts and that proved adequate to represent this contact. Therefore, the weight of the tire is transmitted to the platform only if its current position on the axis of movement of the vehicle is within the platform, i.e. each element of train of loads (p_i) having a position greater than zero relative to the start of the platform and less than the length of platform L will be considered. For the rear tire the same criterion was used by discounting the distance between the axis of the current position x of the tire (see Figure 2).

Figure 2- Representation of the tire contact area by equivalent train of loads

2.5 Dynamic Analysis

The vehicle dynamics including loading from the road roughness, load platform step and platform dynamics are modelled as usual as input forces and the equilibrium equation of motion in the discretized form takes the form, Equation (8):

$$[M]\ddot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + [C]\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) + [K]\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{F}(t)$ mean the load vector (including self-weight and forces imposed by the road to the tires, $[M]$ is the structural mass matrix, $[C]$ is the structural damping matrix and $[K]$ structural stiffness matrix. The displacements vector is represented by \mathbf{x} and the corresponding derivatives by $\ddot{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{x}}$. For the numerical integration of the 2nd order coupled differential equation system, an implicit Newmark scheme was used. The choose time interval is based on road roughness accuracy representations and this results in time intervals several orders of magnitude lower than usual ($\Delta t = 10^{-6}$ s) values assuring good precision to the resulted values.

3 Simulations

In order to represent a real situation to assess the WIM system accuracy, several simulations were performed using different road roughness, vehicle speeds, load platform step's height

and vehicle type for the two models of platform (RPM and FPM). For a defined combination of parameters, the tests consisted on 100 simulations representing the actual variability of the weighting system and to evaluate the system accuracy. Random generation of road roughness and parameters allowed the variability between simulations. After numerical simulations, the mean error, standard deviation, maximum error and RMS error were evaluated for each axle and GVW for each type of vehicle. For the case of weight error per axle, it presented the mean error value for the two axles. The system accuracy is assessed following the COST323 (Jacob *et al.*, 2002): “for each entity (gross weight, single axle, group of axles and axles of a group) the individual relative errors with respect to the static load (weight) or accepted reference values” are calculated as x_i (Equation 9):

$$x_i = \frac{(Wd_i - Ws_i)}{Ws_i} \times 100 \quad (\text{in } \%) \quad (9)$$

where Wd_i and Ws_i are the in-motion measured value and the static (reference) value”

3.1 Vehicle speed influence

This test presents the results of weight errors in case of vehicle speed variations for the models RPM and FPM. It was assumed five different vehicle speeds from 10 km/h to 80 km/h. The road class and step height were fixed. Tables 1 and 2 show the weight errors for vehicles type (a) and (b), respectively.

Table 1- GVW and weight per axle errors for vehicle speed variation and vehicle type (a)

Rigid Platform Model - TYPE (a) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2 mm AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Speed	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
10 Km/h	0.71%	2.73%	7.89%	2.65%	0.72%	2.74%	7.85%	2.65%
20 Km/h	1.06%	3.95%	10.52%	3.82%	1.07%	3.98%	10.58%	3.98%
40 Km/h	3.28%	7.84%	17.82%	7.15%	3.33%	7.94%	18.01%	7.24%
60 Km/h	4.95%	9.75%	22.98%	8.44%	5.02%	8.55%	23.23%	8.55%
80 Km/h	5.55%	12.74%	29.73%	11.52%	5.63%	12.91%	30.15%	11.67%
Flexible Platform Model - TYPE (a) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2 mm AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Speed	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
10 Km/h	0,36%	2,08%	6,85%	2,06%	0,36%	2,12%	6,95%	2,10%
20 Km/h	1,21%	2,77%	7,15%	2,50%	1,19%	2,77%	7,19%	2,51%
40 Km/h	3,28%	7,84%	17,82%	7,15%	3,33%	7,94%	18,01%	7,24%
60 Km/h	3,73%	10,87%	28,13%	10,26%	3,82%	11,10%	27,52%	10,48%
80 Km/h	5,67%	12,00%	27,37%	10,63%	5,63%	10,67%	28,27%	10,67%

One can notice that both vehicle types (a) and (b) presented for this speed spam a good linear fit for the GVW error \times vehicle speed. Either the relation between standard deviation and vehicle speed as the mean weight error per axle and the corresponding standard deviation presented a similar linear behavior for two models of platform. It can be noted that both FPM vehicle types (a) and (b) presented for this speed range a good linear fit for the RMS error at PBT \times vehicle speed. The relationship between the standard deviation and the vehicle speed as the mean axle weight error and the corresponding standard deviation presented a similar linear behavior. For vehicle type (a), it was observed that the errors were close to the RPM value. For the vehicle type (b), the errors presented by the FPM were slightly smaller than the RPM, showing the importance of this modeling.

Table 2- GVW and weight per axle errors for vehicle speed variation and vehicle type (b)

Rigid Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2 mm AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Speed	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
10 Km/h	0.25%	0.70%	2.36%	0.66%	0.23%	0.68%	2.25%	0.64%
20 Km/h	1.12%	3.06%	7.21%	2.86%	1.15%	3.15%	7.46%	2.95%
40 Km/h	3.24%	7.78%	20.41%	7.11%	3.26%	7.88%	20.66%	7.21%
60 Km/h	4.96%	10.91%	35.54%	9.77%	4.92%	10.87%	35.41%	9.74%
80 Km/h	6.19%	13.93%	42.11%	12.54%	6.13%	13.82%	41.70%	12.45%
Flexible Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2 mm AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Speed	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
10 Km/h	0,01%	0,40%	1,22%	0,40%	0,01%	0,41%	1,22%	0,41%
20 Km/h	0,50%	1,02%	3,14%	0,89%	0,55%	1,15%	3,17%	1,02%
40 Km/h	1,08%	3,97%	11,23%	3,97%	1,19%	4,07%	11,44%	3,91%
60 Km/h	2,75%	8,14%	21,69%	7,70%	2,81%	8,17%	22,23%	7,71%
80 Km/h	4,32%	10,53%	25,73%	9,65%	4,22%	10,35%	24,51%	9,50%

3.2 Step height influence

In this test, the step height was varied from -8 mm to +8 mm for constant vehicle speed and road class for the models RPM and FPM. The two vehicle types were tested. Tables 3 and 4 shows the numerical values obtained in this test for vehicles types (a) and (b), respectively.

Table 3- GVW and weight per axle errors for step height variation for vehicle type (a)

Rigid Platform Model - TYPE (a) VEHICLE, SPEED=40 Km/h AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Step	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
-8mm	-9.89%	11.35%	-22.77%	5.59%	-10.04%	11.52%	-23.16%	5.67%
-4mm	-5.31%	7.82%	-22.04%	5.77%	-5.39%	7.94%	-22.33%	5.85%
-2mm	-2.42%	7.66%	-20.71%	7.31%	-2.46%	7.78%	-21.04%	7.78%
2mm	3.28%	7.84%	17.82%	7.15%	3.33%	7.94%	18.01%	7.24%
4mm	5.02%	8.25%	23.05%	6.58%	5.09%	8.37%	23.46%	6.68%
8mm	10.16%	11.92%	23.42%	6.27%	10.32%	12.12%	23.86%	6.38%
Flexible Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, SPEED=40 Km/h AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Step	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
-8mm	-11,28%	13,18%	-25,84%	6,86%	-11,48%	13,41%	-25,96%	6,97%
-4mm	-5,34%	8,08%	-22,71%	6,10%	-5,48%	8,25%	-23,24%	6,20%
-2mm	-3,43%	7,38%	-18,32%	6,57%	-3,48%	7,63%	-19,05%	6,83%
2mm	3,28%	7,84%	17,82%	7,15%	3,33%	7,94%	18,01%	7,24%
4mm	5,31%	8,57%	24,29%	6,76%	5,45%	8,77%	24,80%	6,91%
8mm	12,15%	13,84%	26,13%	6,66%	12,29%	14,05%	26,46%	6,84%

It was verified that for both vehicles types (a) and (b) the step height is an important factor. For the GVW mean error, it was observed a similar linear behavior for both vehicle types that is function of the step height. The mean error of weight per axle presented values slightly higher, but the overall linear behavior was preserved. For vehicle type (a) it was observed error that are slightly lower than those for type (b) vehicle, especially for ± 8 mm step height. For vehicle type (a), it was observed that the errors were somewhat larger than in RPM. For vehicle (b), the errors presented by FPM were smaller than RPM.

Table 4- GVW and weight per axle errors for step height variation for vehicle type (b)

Rigid Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, SPEED=40 Km/h AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Step	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
-8mm	-10.90%	12.30%	-25.39%	5.74%	-11.09%	12.53%	-25.39%	5.85%
-4mm	-5.72%	9.31%	-19.49%	7.38%	-5.81%	9.44%	-20.00%	7.49%
-2mm	-2.47%	7.42%	-17.00%	7.03%	-2.49%	7.50%	-17.47%	7.11%
2mm	3.24%	7.78%	20.41%	7.11%	3.26%	7.88%	20.66%	7.21%
4mm	6.72%	9.84%	20.87%	7.22%	6.83%	9.96%	21.09%	7.29%
8mm	10.62%	12.52%	24.80%	6.67%	10.84%	12.76%	25.25%	6.76%
Flexible Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, SPEED=40 Km/h AND Cn=2 (ROAD CLASS "B")								
Step	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
-8mm	-7,02%	7,75%	-14,62%	3,31%	-7,22%	8,05%	-15,08%	3,58%
-4mm	-3,21%	5,22%	-12,55%	4,14%	-3,23%	5,27%	-12,61%	4,18%
-2mm	-1,75%	4,21%	-12,56%	3,84%	-1,84%	4,33%	-12,46%	3,94%
2mm	1,08%	3,97%	11,23%	3,97%	1,19%	4,07%	11,44%	3,91%
4mm	3,93%	5,52%	13,66%	3,90%	3,93%	5,55%	14,28%	3,94%
8mm	7,10%	8,04%	14,29%	3,79%	7,29%	8,24%	14,39%	3,86%

3.3 Road roughness influence

This test was meant to check the weight errors for different road class. It was varied the road class from A to E (A mean a very smooth good road and E, a poor-quality road. The vehicle speed and step height were fixed. Tables 5 and 6 shows the numerical results for the simulation for vehicle type (a) and for vehicle type (b), respectively.

Table 5- GVW and weight per axle errors for road class variation and vehicle type (a)

Rigid Platform Model - TYPE (a) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2mm AND SPEED=40 Km/h.								
Road Class	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
A ($C_n=1$)	3.05%	4.74%	14.04%	3.64%	3.10%	4.81%	14.22%	3.70%
B ($C_n=2$)	3.28%	7.84%	17.82%	7.15%	3.33%	7.94%	18.01%	7.24%
C ($C_n=3$)	3.60%	13.95%	30.98%	13.54%	3.64%	14.13%	31.58%	13.73%
D ($C_n=4$)	7.14%	29.11%	75.18%	28.36%	7.27%	29.54%	76.37%	28.78%
E ($C_n=5$)	6.94%	48.21%	126.22%	47.95%	7.07%	48.95%	128.21%	48.68%
Flexible Platform Model - TYPE (a) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2mm AND SPEED=40 Km/h.								
Road Class	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
A ($C_n=1$)	3,10%	4,30%	9,83%	2,99%	3,17%	4,39%	9,86%	3,06%
B ($C_n=2$)	3,28%	7,84%	17,82%	7,15%	3,33%	7,94%	18,01%	7,24%
C ($C_n=3$)	3,71%	14,73%	35,41%	14,32%	3,71%	15,13%	35,84%	14,74%
D ($C_n=4$)	4,77%	30,16%	78,59%	29,93%	5,24%	30,82%	78,30%	30,53%
E ($C_n=5$)	3,54%	49,10%	113,07%	49,22%	4,13%	50,32%	117,79%	50,40%

One can notice that both vehicles type (a) and type (b) presented a good exponential fit for GVW RMS error \times class road. The GVW standard deviation presented a similar exponential

behavior. For road classes D and E, the overall errors were very high for FPM even though smaller than RPM.

Table 6- GVW and weight per axle errors for road class variation and vehicle type (b)

Rigid Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2mm AND SPEED=40 Km/h.								
Road Class	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
A ($C_n=1$)	3.12%	4.85%	13.95%	3.73%	3.14%	4.90%	14.04%	3.78%
B ($C_n=2$)	3.24%	7.78%	20.41%	7.11%	3.26%	7.88%	20.66%	7.21%
C ($C_n=3$)	4.39%	14.58%	36.86%	14.12%	4.45%	14.73%	37.15%	14.12%
D ($C_n=4$)	4.38%	26.38%	70.29%	26.14%	4.47%	26.68%	71.61%	26.43%
E ($C_n=5$)	3.01%	66.56%	173.02%	66.83%	3.06%	67.31%	175.70%	67.58%
Flexible Platform Model - TYPE (b) VEHICLE, STEP SIZE=2mm AND SPEED=40 Km/h.								
Road Class	Gross vehicle weight				Weight per Axle			
	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.	Mean Error	RMS Error	Max. Error	Std. Dev.
A ($C_n=1$)	1,90%	2,78%	6,73%	2,04%	1,95%	2,79%	6,19%	1,99%
B ($C_n=2$)	1,08%	3,97%	11,23%	3,97%	1,19%	4,07%	11,44%	3,91%
C ($C_n=3$)	2,93%	8,94%	22,18%	8,48%	3,29%	9,23%	23,15%	8,67%
D ($C_n=4$)	3.09%	14,26%	47,99%	13,99%	3,97%	14,91%	50,04%	14,44%
E ($C_n=5$)	0,02%	32,56%	81,76%	32,72%	0,34%	32,84%	80,78%	33,00%

4 Conclusions

For a greater speed of passage of vehicles in platforms systems, errors are increased as expected. The increase of the RMS error occurred linearly as a function of the speed for the range of 10 to 80 km/ h tested for both types of vehicles for both the rigid and flexible platform models. For the standard deviation, similar behavior was observed. Weighing at very high speeds using only one platform becomes complicated because higher speeds mean little acquisition time for a fixed size platform and this makes it difficult to accurately assess the weight. Step height variations on low maintenance weighing platform systems can lower the maximum speed for weighing measurement and therefore accuracy using the WIM system. It was observed that a good linear adjustment of the step as a function of the mean error of the PBT and the axes in the range of - 8 mm to + 8 mm simulated. For negative step values (below the average level of the lane) the measured weight was below the static and for positive values the measured weight was higher than the reference, this behavior is evidenced in practice. In this study an exponential adjustment of the pavement class was obtained as a function of the RMS error and the standard deviation obtained. As a rule, it has been noted that the use of very rugged road profiles such as classes D and E are not advisable in HS-WIM systems, as this will produce dynamic effects that will compromise accuracy in the measurement system (very high errors obtained for RPM and FPM).

The modeling of platform dynamics is important and affects the final weighing results, especially for type (b) vehicle, which has seen a considerable decrease in relative error values. For example, for the velocity of 40 km / h, class B track, platform step height of + 2mm was obtained RMS error 7.78% for RPM and 3.97% for FPM. It is envisaged that in the simulation of the weighing platform as completely rigid, the impact caused by the passage of the tires thereon is high by exciting the dynamics of the vehicle suspension and consequently generating fluctuations in the measured weight of the vehicle. While in the case of the simulation of the platform as flexible, this seems to have cushioned the impact and

consequently the fluctuation of the force measured around the static weight of the vehicle. For specifically the same case mentioned above of speed of 40 km / h, class B, platform step height of + 2mm, a randomly identical RMS error of 7.84% was obtained for the RPM for the FPM. For a speed of 80 km / h under the same conditions of runway and step, the RMS error was 12.74% for the RPM and 12.00% for the flexible. This shows the importance of modeling the platform dynamics for both vehicles, especially a greater influence on the vehicle of type (b) causing the relative errors evaluated. However, in a few cases, this conclusion was not verified. For vehicle type (a) there were cases of small increase of the evaluated error of the error values depending on the test. It is thought that this may be related to the small mass, small wheel radius or type of suspension(independent). In the same condition of the above case, with a speed of 60 km/h, the RMS error was 9.75% for RPM and 10.87% for FPM.

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